

Open Letter to The Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences

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Abstract

Awarding of the Nobel Prize in Physics represents in our time a certain public recognition of the scientific work done. Nevertheless, i wonder how is this year's decision of The Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences has to be understood?

The Nobel Foundation

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To Whom It May Concern,

Yesterday, October 4, 2022, the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences has decided to award the Nobel Prize in Physics 2022 “.. for experiments with entangled photons ... ”¹ This is a high privilege of the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences and from my point of view needs no further comment, especially if these experiments can be reproduced without difficulties by other study groups. However, the one is honouring scientists for experiments performed while the other is to honour scientist for the interpretation of the data achieved by experiments performed. The Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences is equally honouring scientist for “experiments ... establishing the violation of Bell inequalities ... ”² which is incomprehensible with the best will in the world. It is neither necessary nor possible to dignify Bell's inequality in this context with a single word although it was done nevertheless. Is this decision of the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences a public kowtow, the highest sign of reverence of the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences with respect to Bell's inequality and the CHSH inequality et cetera? This decision would then be equal to an unconditional surrender of human mind before logical fallacies and logical imbecility and would represent one of the worst and most far reaching historical missteps of the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences ever. It is logically not possible and without any sense to ground the concept of non-locality on Bell's inequality, the CHSH inequality, Koch-Specker et cetera. Bell's (see [Barukčić, 2012, 2016a, 2019](#)) inequality, CHSH (see [Barukčić, 2012, 2016a](#)) inequality are mathematically and logically inconsistent and refuted, since years. In other words, it is necessary to be scrupulously careful not to mismatch the concept of non-locality (see [Barukčić, 2020, Barukčić, 2006, 2020b,c](#)) in any way with Bell's inequality, the CHSH inequality et cetera. As already shown several times, especially by my publications, there is no logical contradiction at all between Einstein's general relativity (see [Barukčić, 2016b, 2020a, 2021, 2022](#)) theory and the concept of non-locality.

Sincerely yours

Ilija Barukčić, Horandstrasse, DE-26441 Jever, Germany, October 5, 2022

¹The Nobel Prize in Physics 2022. [NobelPrize.org](#). Nobel Prize Outreach AB 2022. Wed. 5 Oct 2022. <<https://www.nobelprize.org/prizes/physics/2022/summary/>>

²Ibid.

References

- Ilija Barukčić. *N-th index D-dimensional Einstein gravitational field equations. Geometry unchained.* Books on Demand GmbH, Hamburg-Norderstedt, 2020. ISBN 978-3-7526-3526-3. URL <https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:101:1-2020112520101732772093>. BoD Zenodo.
- Ilija Barukčić. Local hidden variable theorem. *Causation*, 1(1):11–17, Dec. 2006. URL <https://www.causation.eu/index.php/causation/article/view/3>.
- Ilija Barukčić. Anti-Bell - Refutation of Bell's theorem: In: Quantum Theory: Reconsideration of Foundations-6 (QTRF6), Växjö, (Sweden), 11-14 June 2012. In *American Institute of Physics - Conference Proceedings*, volume 1508, pages 354–358, Växjö, Sweden, 2012. American Institute of Physics - Conference Proceedings. doi: 10.1063/1.4773147. QTRF 6. Web of Science. Full text: [American Institute of Physics](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. Anti Chsh—Refutation of the Chsh Inequality. *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics*, 04(04):686–696, 2016a. ISSN 2327-4352. doi: 10.4236/jamp.2016.44079. JAMP.
- Ilija Barukčić. Unified field theory. *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics*, 4(88):1379–1438, 8 2016b. doi: 10.4236/jamp.2016.48147. JAMP.
- Ilija Barukčić. Aristotle's law of contradiction and einstein's special theory of relativity. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 9(22):125–143, 3 2019. ISSN 2250-1177. doi: 10.22270/jddt.v9i2.2389. JDDT.
- Ilija Barukčić. Einstein's field equations and non-locality. *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology*, 66(6):146–167, June 2020a. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3907238. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3907238>. Zenodo.
- Ilija Barukčić. Locality and Non locality. *European Journal of Applied Physics*, 2(5):1–13, October 2020b. ISSN 2684-4451. doi: 10.24018/ejphysics.2020.2.5.22. URL <https://ej-physics.org/index.php/ejphysics/article/view/22>. Free full text: [EJAP](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. *N-th index D-dimensional Einstein gravitational field equations. Geometry unchained.*, volume 1. Books on Demand GmbH, Hamburg-Norderstedt, 1 edition, 2020c. ISBN 978-3-7526-4490-6. ISBN-13: 9783752644906 . Free full text (preprint): [ZENODO](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. The causal relationship k. *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 336:09032, 2021. ISSN 2261-236X. doi: 10.1051/mateconf/202133609032. CSCNS2020. Web of Science. Free full text: [EDP Sciences](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. Time and gravitational field. *Causation*, 18(4):5–107, September 2022. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7133124. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7133124>. Zenodo.